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Abstract
<p>This document is the initial version of the IT environment specification and architecture (task T3.3 of ICT4CART). It defines the scope of the ICT4CART IT environment and provides an initial specification of the functions and components thereof. The document provides a high-level architecture as well as more detailed architectures focused on the various components.</p> <p>The ICT4CART IT environment architecture covers data exchange and management aspects, data analytics, semantic interoperability, environment perception models (EPM), and high-precision positioning.</p>

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The document reflects only the authors' view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
3GPP	3 rd Generation Partnership Project
AD	Automated Driving
CAD	Connected Automated Driving
CAM	Cooperative Awareness Message
CAV	Cooperative Automated Vehicle
CEP	Circular Error Probable
C-ITS	Cooperative Intelligent Transport System(s)
CPM	Collective Perception Message
CPS	Collective Perception Service
CVI	Connected Vehicle Insights
DENM	Decentralised Environmental Notification Message
EC	European Commission
EPM	Environment Perception Model
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
ExVe	Extended Vehicle
GA	Grant Agreement
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite System
IBM	International Business Machines
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IoT	Internet of Things
IT	Information Technology
ITS	Intelligent Transport System
IVI	Infrastructure to Vehicle
LDM	Local Dynamic Map
LIDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LTE	Long-Term Evolution
LTE-V	LTE for Vehicles
MAP	Map
MAPEM	Map Extended Message
MEC	Multi-Access Edge Computing
MobiVoc	Open Mobility Vocabulary
NTRIP	Network Transport of RTCM via Internet Protocol
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
QoS	Quality of Service
RSU	Roadside Unit
RTCM	Radio Technical Commission for Maritime Services
RTK	Real-Time Kinematic
SKOS	Simple Knowledge Organisation System
SPARQL	SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language
SPAT	Signal Phase and Time
SPATEM	Signal Phase and Time Extended Message
TCC	Traffic Control Centre
VMS	Variable Message Sign(s)
VRU	Vulnerable Road User
WP	Work Package

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Executive Summary

The aim of the ICT4CART project is to design, implement and test in real-life conditions a versatile ICT infrastructure that will enable the transition towards higher levels of automation. It focuses on four high-value use cases:

1. UC1 - Smart parking and IoT services,
2. UC2 - Dynamic adaptation of vehicle automation level based on infrastructure information,
3. UC3 - Intersection crossing (urban) and lane merging (highway),
4. UC4 - Cross border interoperability between Austria and Italy.

The above use cases will be implemented and tested in four test sites in Austria, Germany, Italy, and at the Austria-Italy border.

This document is the first version of the IT environment specification and architecture (task T3.3 of ICT4CART). It defines the scope of the ICT4CART IT environment and provides an initial specification of the functions and components thereof. The document provides a high-level architecture as well as more detailed architectures focused on the various components.

The ICT4CART IT environment architecture covers data exchange and management aspects, data analytics, semantic interoperability, environment perception models (EPM), and high-precision positioning. In order to design a generic architecture, we started by identifying the commonalities between the various use cases in terms of the data flows. This further allowed us to identify the common architectural components and data exchange standards to comply with across the test sites.

The functional viewpoint of the IT environment architecture foresees two types of functions:

- Core IT Services: These are low-level functions that are common across use cases and pilot sites. As such, they require a high level of standardisation. Core services include cooperative intelligent transport system (C-ITS) services, EPM building and fusion, service provider gateways, geo service, location correction, message brokering, and analytics.
- Applications: These are services that are specific to the use cases. They typically make use of the core IT services. Applications include, but are not limited to, automation level road clearance, smart parking, and fleet management.

The IT environment architecture should cope with various connectivity requirements (e.g., latency, throughput, etc.). Therefore, it should be distributed over both cloud and multi-access edge computing (MEC) infrastructures. While cloud services will provide large-scale and non-time critical services (e.g., service provider gateways, semantic interoperability, geo service, etc.), MEC servers will host localised services requiring low-latency, such as C-ITS services, and EPM services. Such MEC servers are located at the edge of the network, connected to the base stations of the cellular network. They provide computation closer to the vehicles, thereby reducing latency for mission-critical data. As a vehicle is moving, it should remain connected to the closest MEC server to minimise latency. Such vehicle-MEC handover will be facilitated through the use of a geo service that includes a registry of MEC and cloud services with their spatial locations and extents.

Environment perception models will be used in ICT4CART to communicate in real time the set of objects involved in the traffic at a given location (e.g., intersection, toll station, etc.). The ETSI TS 103 324 standard specification of collective perception services should be adopted for the encoding and exchange of EPMs. This standard is currently under development. But a number of ICT4CART project partners are involved in this effort. It is recommended in this document that we should consider the current draft of the standard and contribute to its development through the implementation and testing of the ICT4CART use cases.

Data analytics aim to provide additional knowledge based on data received by or exchanged through the IT environment. An initial list of analytics is identified in this document, including:

- Prediction of parking availability,
- Prediction of charging station availability,
- Motion prediction for environment perception models,
- Risk maps for the adaptation of automation level.

Precise localisation in ICT4CART will be based on the Real-Time Kinematic (RTK) technique, which enhances the precision of the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS). In the German test site, an RTK reference station will be collocated with each 4G/5G radio base station. The distance between different 4G/5G radio base stations are typically no more than 10 km. In the Austrian test site, the precise localisation service is completely based on a Network RTK approach, because the distance between the different RTK reference stations is significantly larger than 10 km in the case of an external service provider.

Interoperability will be facilitated in ICT4CART through the adoption of standard data models and formats, and through the specification of common service interfaces. Semantic interoperability will rely on the provision of a semantic framework that provides common vocabularies and ontologies for use as values of data fields.

1 Introduction

1.1 Aim of the Project

Today, significant and rapid advances in both telecom and IT industries can be accredited to fast-growing disruptive technologies. Amongst these, the ETSI ITS-G5 technology appears to be quite mature. Moreover, the 5G technology is evolving rapidly, while LTE-Vehicle (LTE-V) features low cost and rapid deployment since it can utilise existing LTE technology. In light of the above, several ICT challenges related to connectivity, data management, cyber-security and ICT infrastructure architectures need to be addressed in order to enable road vehicle automation. Thus, it is of utmost importance for the vehicle automation to work on the direction of advancing the digital and ICT infrastructure, taking into consideration the limitations in both resources and investments in the physical transport infrastructure.

ICT4CART aims to address the gaps to deployment by bringing together key players from automotive, telecom and IT industries. The goal is to shape the ICT landscape for connected and automated road transport and to boost the EU competitiveness and innovation in this area.

The main objective of ICT4CART is to design, implement and test in real-life conditions a versatile ICT infrastructure that will enable the transition towards higher levels of automation (up to L4) addressing existing gaps and working with specific key ICT elements, namely hybrid connectivity, data management, cyber-security, data privacy and accurate localisation. ICT4CART builds on high-value use cases (in both urban and highway environments) that will be demonstrated and validated in real-life conditions at the test sites in Austria, Germany and Italy. Cross-border interoperability will be tested in a dedicated test site at the Austrian-Italian border.

1.2 Purpose of the document

This document is the first version of the IT environment specification and architecture (task T3.3 of ICT4CART). It defines the scope of the ICT4CART IT environment and provides an initial specification of the functions and components thereof. The document provides a high-level architecture as well as more detailed architectures focused on the various components. This document is considered as a guide for the actual implementation of the IT services and tools within work package 5 (WP5). The actual implementation will be reported in future deliverables (D5.X).

1.3 Intended Readership

This document is a public deliverable of the ICT4CART project. It is primarily targeted to the project partners involved in the design and development of the ICT4CART architecture. The document may also be of interest to any reader who wishes to be informed about the ICT4CART architecture.

1.4 Connected Automated Driving

According to the Gear 2030 Discussion Paper¹, the concept of “automated driving” (AD) is often associated with “connected automated driving” (CAD), usually being talked about in the same breath, but in fact, they must be encountered and considered as different technologies.

Automated driving senses its environment but it does not provide vehicle or infrastructure interaction

¹ Gear 2030 Discussion Paper: <https://ibm.biz/BdzKQy>

nor cooperation or exchange of data. However, it can be considered as a substantial contributor to the integration with other important evolution of road transport such as shared mobility concepts.

Connected automated driving operates within a network with other vehicles and devices along the road. It aims to enable interoperable networked wireless communications amongst the vehicles and the infrastructure. Therefore, connected automated driving is considered as *“one of the key technologies and major technological advancements influencing and shaping our future mobility, our quality of life”* [ERTAC19]. CAD is also expected to contribute to the implementation of the European Transport policy, towards increasing the overall efficiency (e.g., in terms of congestion, decarbonisation, and social inclusiveness) and safety of the transport systems by dint of automation.

1.5 Scope of the IT Environment

The ICT4CART IT Environment covers the following functionality required by connected automated driving:

- Common interfaces and services for data exchange through multi-access edge or cloud computing,
- Common or generic analytics platforms and algorithms (e.g., traffic jam analysis, parking and charging station availability prediction, etc.),
- Building environment perception models,
- Common services for precise localisation,
- Semantic interoperability.

1.6 Structure of this Document

This document is structured as follows. After this introduction, Section 2 provides the background information about the ICT4CART high-level architecture. Section 3 provides a brief overview of the use cases specified within the project and pilot test sites. Section 4 summarises the functional and non-functional requirements pertaining to the IT environment. Section 5 reports on the specification of the IT environment and introduces its main components. The subsequent Sections focus on various aspects of the IT environment: environment perception models (Section 6), data analytics required to support the use cases (Section 7), semantic interoperability (Section 8), precise localisation (Section 9).

2 ICT4CART ICT Architecture

The main goal of the ICT4CART project, as per the description of work, is to develop an innovative and generic ICT architecture that will enable the transition towards higher levels of automation (L3 to L4). Although the target architecture will be deployed in limited pilot sites, it is aimed to provide a reference architecture for pan-European deployment.

The ICT4CART ICT architecture is aimed to operate seamlessly with different communication technologies, i.e., ad-hoc networks (ETSI ITS-G5) and cellular networks (LTE/5G), referred to as hybrid communication. Low-latency services will be supported through multi-access edge computing (MEC) in cellular networks or similar functionality in ad-hoc networks. The ICT architecture will enable high-value use-cases for automated driving, such as smart parking, intersection crossing in urban environments, lane-merging in highway scenarios, and cross-border interoperability (cf. Section 3). A high-level view of the ICT architecture is provided in deliverable D3.1 [D3.1], including functional, information, and communication viewpoints.

The ICT architecture covers the following three aspects (sub-architectures):

- Telecommunication, which is the subject of deliverable D3.2 [D3.2],
- IT environment, which is the subject of the present document,
- Privacy and cyber-security, which is the subject of deliverable D3.4 [D3.4].

This Section aims to provide a summary of the overall ICT4CART ICT architecture. The purpose is to provide context information for the IT environment specified in this document. For further details about the ICT architecture, please refer to deliverable D3.1 [D3.1].

2.1 High-level architecture

Figure 1 – ICT4CART High-Level Overview from D3.1 [D3.1].

Figure 1 illustrates the ICT4CAT overall ICT architecture. It shows the basic components involved in the ICT4CAT system and their interactions. The main components are the vehicles, infrastructure (sensors and processing units) and IT services (such as an OEM backend or other service providers). The basic communication technologies that are used are LTE/5G (cellular) and ITS-G5 (ad-hoc). When using 5G, slicing may be used to provide the quality of service (QoS) required for the kind of information to be transported, which is represented by the dashed lines in the figure. There can be slices, e.g., for low-latency communication (short dashes in the figure) or high-throughput communication (lines with longer dashes in the figure). As slicing is a 5G feature, it is not available when using LTE or ITS-G5. For further details on the communication, see Section 2.3.

Hybrid connectivity, i.e., using ITS-G5 and LTE/5G in parallel, is also depicted in the figure, as the infrastructure may provide information via both communication channels. Vehicles may retrieve/receive information using both communication pathways, either from the same source or from different sources. The vehicles in Figure 1 are either not connected, connected with ITS-G5 (G5), with LTE/5G (5G), or with both (5G+G5). A vehicle-to-vehicle (V2V) connection is possible via ITS-G5.

The road is equipped with roadside units (RSUs), connected sensors, and connected traffic signs (e.g., traffic lights). LTE/5G base stations receive and transmit data via the cellular network (green lines). ITS-G5 RSUs receive and transmit data via ITS-G5 (blue lines). Sensors and traffic lights are connected either via fibre cables (orange lines), cellular network, or via ITS-G5.

Figure 1 also shows the concept of MEC servers. MEC servers are located at the edge level of the network close to a base station of a cellular network, providing computation closer to end devices (in the ICT4CAT use cases: vehicles), thereby avoiding time-consuming transmission of data via the Internet. This concept decreases latency, especially for mission-critical data, when compared to using a cloud server anywhere in the network.

Similar functionality to MEC servers can be provided by the processing capabilities of road infrastructure (e.g., sensors) in combination with RSUs. This is shown in the left part of the figure. For the sake of simplicity, these processing units are also denoted as MEC here. An RSU is an ITS-G5 communication unit on the infrastructure side. Such MEC servers in combination with RSUs can run ICT4CAT applications or services in close proximity to the vehicle with low delays (relatively to cloud services). Information from the OEM Backend, service providers, and other cloud services ("..." cloud in Figure 1) can be received through the internet.

2.2 Functional view

The ICT4CAT architecture consists of a collection of functional blocks. The functional view, provided in Figure 2, organises the functional blocks into groups according to their common purpose: supporting services, sensors and actuators, applications, core services, hybrid wireless network, cooperative automated vehicle (CAV), and security & privacy. The individual functional components are described in Deliverable 3.1 Section 3 [D3.1]. The Core IT Services are of particular relevance to the IT Environment. Data flows are not depicted in this diagram but will be shown later in Section 3.2.

Figure 2 – ICT4CART Functional Architecture

2.3 Communication view

Deliverable 3.1 [D3.1] also presents a communication view of the architecture. In essence, communication partners are viewed as ITS stations, and communication is performed using ITS messages via any transmission channel (hybrid communication), while only ITS-G5 and LTE/5G are used in this project. Details on the different types of messages used in the project and which devices can send them are presented later in Section 3.2. Further details on the hybrid communication can be found in Section 5 of [D3.1] and in deliverable 3.2 [D3.2].

2.4 Cyber-Security & Privacy View

In deliverable D3.1[D3.1], multiple technologies for cyber-security and data privacy have been presented, such as the cyber security supervision service, the identity and access management service, and the data privacy mechanism based on group signatures with selective linkability. In this document, the integration of cyber-security and data privacy into the IT environment is not covered, for details on this please refer to section 6 of deliverable D3.1 [D3.1] and the deliverable D3.4 [D3.4].

3 Pilot Sites and Use Cases

3.1 Overview of Use Cases and Pilot Sites

This section provides an overview on the ICT4CART pilot sites and use cases, useful to understand the context of the IT environment. Further details can be found in deliverable D2.1, “Specification of Use Cases” [D2.1]. In this section, we present the pilot sites and describe the use cases and scenarios that will be implemented in each of them. References to scenario numbers (in the format “SCNx.y”) from D2.1 are used throughout.

3.1.1 Austrian Test Site

The Austrian Test Site includes 20km of the A2 motorway between *Laßnitzhöhe* and Graz city as illustrated in the map of Figure 3.

Figure 3 – Map of the Austrian Test Site

The test site is equipped with:

- C-ITS road-side units: variable message signs (VMS) information, road works warnings, events, etc.,
- Video cameras: traffic management, single vehicle detection,
- Single-vehicle counters,
- Environmental sensors.

The Austrian test site will focus on the transition from L3 to L2 automation (scenario SCN2.1 – *DAVAGRZ*). The scenario consists in a vehicle driving with an active automated driving function L3 on the highway, encountering a restricting condition. The function will hand over to the driver, thereby performing an adaptation from L3 to L2. The function will use data streams from the highway infrastructure, exchanging messages with the traffic control centre via road-side infrastructure, to detect restricting conditions as early as possible in order to initiate an early in-time handover procedure, as indicated in Figure 4.

An optional MEC server may be included to cater for future scalability and latency requirements to improve the available features. All data flows implemented will be available on the complete Austrian

highway network.

Figure 4 – Austrian Test Site digital infrastructure

3.1.2 German Test Site

The German test site is located in the City of Ulm and its surroundings. Figure 5 illustrates examples of possible roads to be used for testing activities. In blue is the motorway (Autobahn A8), in yellow are rural roads, in green are intra-urban roads, and in light blue are the radio sites and the test site bounding box. Figure 6 shows the crossroad that will be used for the demonstration of the virtual mirror use case.

Figure 5 – Test Roads in the City of Ulm

Figure 6 – Crossroad in the City of Ulm

The test site is equipped with an LTE cellular test network with:

- MEC server in the northern parts of Ulm operated by NOKIA,
- Parking guidance system for parking garages with open interfaces operated by the City of Ulm,
- Two infrastructure sensor units operated by Ulm University,
- Two fully automated (L4) research vehicles operated by Ulm University,
- Traffic light (operated by the City of Ulm) to be equipped with communication means for traffic light status communication to connected vehicles by SWARCO during the project,
- Charging station occupancy information operated by a daughter-company of the City of Ulm.

The coverage of the 4G/LTE test network will be provided by NOKIA, including the corresponding 5G radio sites. NOKIA's test network is available from Autobahn A8 to inner city, covering many types of roads from motorway to small inner-city side streets.

The German test site will focus on:

- Automated parking services (SCN1.1 - SPiOTULM), more specifically the link between fleet management with respect to mobility hubs (e.g., near a main station), mobility demand as in car/ride sharing, and IoT to provide services like charging/refuelling in combination with parking.
- Seamless integration of different communication technologies (ITS-G5 and 5G/LTE), which will be demonstrated at one traffic light crossing (SCN3.1.a – VMULM).
- Exploitation of hybrid connectivity (ITS-G5 and 5G/LTE) and MEC to create 360° awareness around the vehicle with very low latency, creating a kind of “virtual mirror” to support the automated vehicle while crossing an intersection (SCN3.1.a – VMULM). This “virtual mirror” consists of an environment perception model of all road users at the intersection, finally enabling the crossing of intersections in an automated way involving mixed traffic.
- Precise localisation in urban and highway location (SCN3.4 – PPRTK).

3.1.3 Italian Test Site

The Italian test site includes the City of Verona and the A22 motorway (Autostrada del Brennero)). The A22 motorway runs across the city of Verona, where ICT4CART plans a C-ITS test site in urban environment.

Figure 7 – Map of the Italian Test Site, View of A22 Motorway

Figure 8 – View of A22 Motorway and of Trento Centro exit to be used in ICT4CART

The toll road A22 is a 314-km-long Italian highway running from Brennero to Modena (see Figure 7). A 9-km stretch along the motorway, south of Trento, is specifically equipped with C-ITS systems.

The test site is equipped with:

- 8 RSUs from Brennero to Modena featuring C-ITS Day 1² services via ETSI ITS-G5,
- Roadside stations (RS) for V2I communication,
- Legacy road sensors and service centre,
- Full cellular network coverage in the C-ITS interested area,
- GNSS RTK precise position system, which may additionally be provided by CRF.

The City of Verona is equipped with:

- 142 connected traffic lights stations, of which 62 are centralised,
- More than 600 sensors on the territory,
- RSUs with ITS-G5,
- Automatic Vehicle Identification system,
- Platforms for integration that support monitoring of additional data sources,
- Parking identification system,
- Several VMSs in the city,
- SOS columns + 1 emergency lay-by and Video Detection System on the road network.

Figure 9 – City of Verona

Wind-Tre will provide the LTE cellular network with MEC server capabilities to be integrated into the Italian Test Site according to the ICT4CART infrastructure architecture. LINKS will provide the on-board units which are offering hybrid connectivity compliant to the ICT4CART architecture, while CRF will provide two vehicle prototypes (one connected and automated, and one connected).

Within ICT4CART, the test site will focus on:

- Dynamic adaptation of vehicle automation level both in motorway and in urban environments (SCN2.2 – DAVATRN and SCN2.3 – DAVACDV).

² Day 1 Services: <https://ec.europa.eu/transport/sites/transport/files/themes/its/doc/c-its-platform-final-report-january-2016.pdf>

- In the urban environment scenario, the test site will focus on the road stretches before and at the exits from the motorway to toll or gas stations. The objective is to provide the information needed to enable the connected and automated vehicle to refine its driving actions, for example adapting its velocity on the exit ramp, selecting the less congested toll station lane, and possibly downscaling the automation level (or even disengaging automation).
- In the urban environment scenario, the ICT4CART infrastructure will monitor an urban intersection, detecting road users and communicating with the vehicles so that they may adapt their behaviours to avoid dangers and potential collisions with other vehicles or vulnerable road users (VRUs), such as pedestrians and bicycles.
- Lane merging at main road entrances (SCN3.3 – LMBRE) to help the connected vehicle approach the best toll lane, considering both traffic information provided by the infrastructure and dynamic information relative to the toll stations (e.g., open lane and payment methods accepted).
- Intersection crossing, delivering dynamic traffic light information (SCN3.2 – GLOSA) to vehicles but also all kinds of traffic data that may be used to reduce incidents by warning drivers about queuing traffic in blind spots or dangerous situations ahead (SCN3.1.b – VMCDV).
- Smart parking (SCN1.2 - SPlOTCDV), focusing on connectivity and precise positioning aspects, in order to move towards possible future in-vehicle application and to get accurate parking information from city infrastructure, potentially applicable to automated vehicles.

3.1.4 Cross-border Test Site (Austria-Italy).

The fourth test site is located at the border between Austria and Italy. The location of this site is shown in the map of Figure 10, with dark red bounding box.

Figure 10 – Map of the Cross-border Test Site

The goal of this pilot site is to test and demonstrate the cross-border interoperability and functionalities of the developed ICT4CART infrastructure.

In one country, an automated driving function may use information received from the ITS-G5 network, while in the neighbouring country it may use information from the cellular network. The purpose is to show that while crossing the border, the operation of this function is kept uninterrupted, due to the ICT4CART infrastructure capabilities.

ICT4CART will address the handover between different back-ends, aiming at the development of a pan-European solution. The basic feature will be to seamlessly change back-end connections while

driving between Austria and Italy and vice versa.

Cross border tests will focus on scenario SCN4.1 – DAVAXBR:

- Precise positioning,
- ITS-G5 Day 1,
- 4G/LTE tests analogous to ITS-G5 Day 1,
- Dynamic adaptation of vehicle automation.

3.2 Commonalities across Use Cases

Figure 11 shows an overview of the common data flows across the use cases introduced above. This diagram does not aim to be exhaustive. Rather, it aims to depict the main data exchanges within the scope of the IT environment.

Figure 11 – Common Data Flow across Use Cases

The data flows illustrated in Figure 11 are explained below, using same numbering convention as in the figure.

1. Road users or sensors may submit data to a road-side unit (RSU) about the current “driving environment” (e.g., road users, obstacles, traffic signs, parking availability, etc.).
2. Consumer vehicles equipped with ITS-G5 communication may receive data directly from an RSU (e.g., CPM, DENM, SPATEM, MAPEM) or other vehicles (e.g., CAM, CPM).
3. One or multiple RSUs and road sensors may push their data to a MEC server in their vicinity using LTE/4G/5G.
4. Consumer vehicles equipped with LTE/4G/5G communication may receive environment perception models (e.g., CPM) from the MEC server.
5. A cloud platform may receive data from MEC servers and service providers (e.g., parking providers, traffic control centres, etc.) to create large-scale maps and predictions (e.g., parking availability predictions, traffic jam analysis, etc.).
6. Vehicles equipped with LTE/4G/5G communication may receive data from the cloud platform

about traffic jams in their vicinities, parking availability predictions, etc. These may be used for long-term (strategic) decisions and for automation level adaptation.

The IT environment aims to support the above data flows across all the use cases, pilot sites, and in compliance with existing standards.

4 IT Environment Requirements

The purpose of this Section is to provide a summary of the requirements pertaining to the IT environment. The IT environment requirements are a subset of the ICT4CART architecture requirements identified in the project deliverable D2.3 [D2.3]. D2.3 covers all the system requirements related to hybrid connectivity, the IT environment (data flows, management and analytics), and cyber-security and data privacy.

The goal of the ICT4CART IT environment is to ensure that data is exchanged and processed according to the use case requirements and regardless of the specific underlying network technologies (i.e., cellular, ad-hoc, or hybrid) or hardware components (e.g., RSU or MEC). The IT environment must interconnect vehicles, road infrastructure and other devices with services to be developed during the project (e.g., smart parking predictive analytics, EPM building), and existing external services (e.g., parking availability data). This Section summarises the requirements required for this purpose.

4.1 Functional Requirements

A summary of the functional requirements pertaining to the IT environment, as identified in deliverable 2.3 [D2.3], is provided in Table 1. The table shows the parent requirements (numbered as “R-{xy}”) and their child requirements (numbered as “R-IT-{xy}”).

Table 1 – Functional Requirements Pertaining to the IT Environment.

ID	Name	Description	Scope	Priority
R-05	IT environment	The ICT4CART IT environment shall enable the exchange of data needed for automated driving purposes respecting the required performances (e.g. latency, integrity, throughput availability, interoperability, etc.)		
R-IT-01	Vehicle to IT environment data flow	Depending on the use case or scenario, a vehicle may submit data to the IT environment's core services.	Vehicle and core services	1
R-IT-03	Infrastructure to IT environment data flow	Infrastructure data shall be submitted to the relevant IT environment core services.	Road sensors, RSUs and core services	1
R-IT-06	Low latency services	Services requiring low latency data exchanges shall run in Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) platforms	Core services and supporting services	1
R-IT-07	MEC discovery	ICT4CART vehicles shall be able to exchange data with a MEC server to access ICT4CART services	Geo Service	1
R-IT-08	MEC service discovery	MEC services shall be discoverable by vehicles	Geo Service	
R-IT-09	MEC handover	Vehicles shall be handed over to the most appropriate MEC server as they are travelling.	Geo Service	3

	R-IT-13	External connectivity	ICT4CART services may receive data from (external) traffic and parking services	Core services	2
	R-IT-14	SP gateways	When appropriate, data from external service providers (e.g., parking garages) should be provided to the IT environment services through a common "standardised" service provider gateway.	SP Gateway	2
	R-IT-20	Vocabulary	Common vocabularies should be provided to, and shared amongst, the ICT4CART IT services.	Semantic framework	1
	R-IT-22	Semantic service	A semantic service may be implemented to deliver the ICT4CART vocabularies	Semantic framework	3
	R-06	Perception models	The ICT4CART IT environment shall build and provide environment perception models for use by connected vehicles, and possible applications and services pertaining to the use cases.		
	R-IT-10	EPM data	EPMS shall be built based on available data from ICT4CART vehicles and/or road sensors.	EPM Building and Fusion	1
	R-07	Real time data analytics	The ICT4CART IT environment shall enable real-time analytics. Real-time constraints will be defined during the requirement specifications.		
	R-IT-15	Smart parking analytics	ICT4CART analytics services shall support the prediction of parking and/or charging station availability	Analytics services, smart parking	1
	R-IT-16	Traffic analytics	ICT4CART analytics services shall support traffic jam detection and analysis	Analytics Services	2
	R-15	Localisation system	The ICT4CART localisation system will combine standard GNSS with Real Time Kinematic (RTK) information and information from other sources to enhance precision.		
	R-IT-17	Precise positioning using physical reference stations	MEC server servers shall distribute correction information of the nearest physical reference station	Location correction data	2

	R-IT-18	Precise positioning using virtual reference stations	MEC server shall distribute correction information of the virtual reference stations by using a public service.	Location correction data	2
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4.2 Non-Functional Requirements

A summary of the non-functional requirements pertaining to the IT environment, as identified in deliverable 2.3 [D2.3], is provided in Table 2. The table shows the parent requirements (numbered as “R-{xy}”) and their child requirements (numbered as “R-IT-{xy}”). Some child non-functional requirements are derived from parent functional requirements. Such parent functional requirements are greyed in the table.

Table 2 – Non-Functional Requirements Pertaining to the IT Environment.

ID	Name	Description	Scope	Priority
R-04	Network architecture	In ICT4CART, a flexible network architecture shall be deployed, which will allow for a QoS and isolation for different applications with different required performances levels.		
R-05	<i>IT environment</i>	<i>The ICT4CART IT environment shall enable the exchange of data needed for automated driving purposes respecting the required performances (e.g. latency, integrity, throughput availability, interoperability, etc.)</i>		
R-IT-02	Standardised vehicle to IT Environment data flow	Data submitted by vehicles shall comply with industry standards	Vehicles and core services	3
R-IT-04	Standardised infrastructure to IT environment data flow	Data exchange between the infrastructure and the IT environment should comply with industry standard protocols, interfaces, and data formats.	Vehicle, core services, supporting services and applications	3
R-IT-05	Appropriate deployment	ICT4CART services should be deployed on appropriate computing platforms (cloud, MEC, etc.) depending on the use case requirements (namely latency requirements).	Core services, supporting services and applications	2
R-IT-19	Semantic interoperability	The IT services and applications shall be interoperable.	Core services and supporting services,	1

				semantic framework	
	R-IT-21	Standardised vocabularies	The ICT4CART vocabularies should be based on existing/standard vocabularies	Semantic framework	1
	R-IT-23	Message broker	When needed, the algorithm used in the message broker shall be common and according to C-Roads platform specifications. In case of non-standard features this is not required.	Message Broker	2
	R-06	Perception models	<i>The ICT4CART IT environment shall build and provide environment perception models for use by connected vehicles, and possible applications and services pertaining to the use cases.</i>		
		EPM delay	EPMs shall be computed and delivered with delays acceptable by the target application.	EPM Building and Fusion	1
		EPM exchange	EPMs exchange format shall follow standards, i.e. Collective Perception Messages (CPM)	EPM Building and Fusion	3
	R-09	Data mobility and Privacy preservation	ICT4CART shall consider the European Cloud initiative and Digital Single Market Free Flow Data initiative from the EC.		
	R-13	Privacy preservation	ICT4CART will consider the findings of the C-ITS platform and the data protection legal framework of General Data Protection Regulation to preserve privacy aspects.		
	R-21	Assurance Level	Information delivered into the vehicle that is used in safety-critical applications should be validated accordingly, thereby complying with the necessary assurance level requirement by the vehicle (ASIL for instance).		
	R-22	Market needs	ICT4CART shall provide a minimum level of performance (based on a framework of "performance elements") to be guarantees on each market services. Services shall reach a minimum level in accordance with the marked needs.		

5 IT Environment Architecture

Based on the requirements summarised in Section 4, we now elaborate the IT environment architecture.

5.1 Functional Viewpoint

The functional viewpoint of the overall ICT4CART ICT architecture is illustrated in Figure 2, which is described in more detail in the project deliverable D3.1 “ICT4CART Reference Architecture” [D3.1]. In this document, we focus on the IT environment functions in the infrastructure, which are represented in Figure 12.

Figure 12 – ICT4CART Functional Architecture

The IT environment functions are split into two categories:

- **Core IT Services:** These are low-level functions that are common across use cases and pilot sites. As such, they require a high-level of standardisation. Core services include:
 - **C-ITS Services:** Collective services such as environmental notification services and collective perception services.
 - **Risk Maps for Automation Level Adaptation:** Functions for extracting information pertaining to the existence of absence of risks that may require or suggest the adaptation of the driving automation level of a vehicle, such as handing over the driving of the vehicle to the human driver or vice versa.
 - **EPM Building and Fusion:** Functions for extracting and aggregating relevant information about the environment in which vehicles are operating. Such functions use data from a variety of sources, such as sensors data, road users, etc.
 - **SP Gateways:** Service provider gateways provide access to data from service providers such as parking garages, charging station services, etc.
 - **Geo Service:** Some of the services provided by the IT environment (e.g., services deployed on MEC servers) are bound to predefined geographic areas. As a vehicle is moving, from one area to another, it needs to be handed over to the relevant services (e.g., MEC server). The geo service is responsible for such function.
 - **Location Correction:** Provides precise localisation.
 - **Message Broker:** Allows messages to be exchanged in a pub/sub or broadcast way.
 - **Analytics:** Functions for extracting additional knowledge (e.g., predictions) from data exchanged through the IT environment.
- **Applications:** These are services that are specific to use cases. They typically make use of the

core IT services. They may be deployed anywhere, such as in the OEM backend or in the vehicle. Applications include, but are not limited to:

- Automation Level Adaptation: A function that instructs the vehicle to adjust its driving automation level, based on the surrounding situations or risks (provided by the risk maps for automation level adaptation functionality).
- Smart Parking: A function that provides parking assistance to vehicles.
- Fleet Management: A function for managing the operations of a fleet of vehicles. This includes the planning of parking and charging tasks.

5.2 Component Viewpoint

A high-level component viewpoint of the ICT4CART IT environment architecture is shown in Figure 13. As can be seen, the IT environment is distributed over two types of platforms: cloud and MEC. Services required with low latency or limited geospatial extent (≤ 50 milli seconds) should be deployed on MEC servers, others should be deployed on the cloud. As can be seen in the architectural diagram of Figure 13, vehicles should communicate with MEC services directly since MEC services and applications require low latency. However, they may communicate with cloud services off-board access (see Section 5.2.1).

Please note that the vehicle is not considered as part of the IT environment. Rather, it is considered as a client.

Figure 13 – ICT4CART IT Environment Architecture – Component Viewpoint

The main components of the ICT4CART IT environment architecture are introduced below and are further elaborated in subsequent Sections.

- Off-Board Access: Acts as an intermediary between the vehicle and the external world, providing secure and privacy-preserving data exchanges.
- Semantic Framework: Aims to provide reference vocabularies for use across the IT environment.

- Geo Service: Provides functionality to facilitate the handover of a vehicle from one MEC server to another as the vehicle is moving from one MEC area to another.
- Parking and Charging Station Service Gateway: Provides unified access to parking and charging station availability information, including predictions and recommendations, based on data from multiple service providers.
- Risk Maps for Automation Level Adaptation: Provide information required for the adaptation of the vehicle’s automation level. This includes traffic jams, incidents, etc.
- Collective Perception Service: Provides environment perception models to vehicles.
- Environmental Notification Service: Provides environmental notifications to vehicles.

The above components are further detailed in the subsequent sections 5.2.x.

5.2.1 Off-Board Access

As per the Extended Vehicle (ExVe) Concept [ISO19]³, communication between a vehicle and cloud services should be secured and safeguarded by means of off-board access. Off-board access acts as a secured intermediary between the vehicle and cloud services. It may be an OEM backend, or a dedicated platform, such IBM Watson IoT Connected Vehicle Insights (CVI)⁴.

The role of the off-board access is to:

- Protect the personal data of the vehicle owner or driver,
- Ensure safe and secure functioning of the vehicle,
- Provide additional services to the vehicle.

Off-board access should be used in the ICT4CART IT environment as specified in the ExVe concept.

5.2.2 Semantic Framework

Semantic interoperability between the various components of the ICT4CART IT environment requires that all the components share common vocabularies when they communicate with each other.

Figure 14 – ICT4CART Semantic Framework

³ What is the Extended Vehicle Concept? <https://cardatafacts.eu/extended-vehicle-concept/>

⁴ IBM Watson IoT CVI Documentation: <https://ibm.biz/BdzPa9>

An initial proposal for the semantic framework is proposed in the architectural diagram of Figure 14. The core component of this architecture is the common ontology base. This may be stored in an appropriate repository such as a triple store. A semantic server or query engine may be used to query the ontologies.

We leave the implementation of the semantic service and repository (triple store) optional at this stage of the project. Whether these will be implemented or not and what technologies to use will follow the following rationale.

1. If the vocabularies to be used in ICT4CART are all existing (standard) ontologies, already hosted and accessible in third party systems, and do not require further processing (mapping, reasoning, etc.), then we may simply refer to those ontologies without copying them in a triple store. A semantic service will not be needed in this case.
2. If the identified ontologies need to be extended or processed (e.g., by adding mappings across ontologies), then the ontologies should be stored in a dedicated relevant repository, such as a triple store or database.
3. If, in addition to 2, the ontologies need to be queried (e.g., retrieve concept definition, relationships between concepts, etc.), then a suitable semantic service shall be implemented. This may be a SPARQL [PS08] endpoint, or a custom Rest service.

The content of the ontologies will be defined at later stages of the project as the messages exchanged throughout the IT environment are being defined and refined, and requirements for controlled vocabularies are being identified.

Examples of concepts that may be covered by the vocabularies include but are not limited to:

- Types of objects detected and included in environment perception models,
- Event and traffic situation types included in environmental alerts and in automation level risk maps,
- Parking and parking spot types, etc.

Vocabularies used in the project shall whenever possible be based on existing and standard vocabularies and ontologies, such as the Open Mobility Vocabulary, known as MobiVoc [BW18]. We also recommend simple ontology models, such as the Simple Knowledge Organisation System (SKOS) [MB05]. Complex ontologies tend to be very difficult to populate and use.

5.2.3 Geo Service

As explained in Section 2, the ICT4CART architecture includes multi-access edge computing (MEC) servers. MEC servers are situated close to the base stations of a cellular network, providing computation closer to the vehicles, thereby avoiding time-consuming transmission of data via the internet. This concept decreases latency, especially for mission-critical data, when compared to using a cloud server anywhere in the network. MEC servers are then used to provide localised services, i.e., pertaining to relatively small areas (typically a diameter of a few kilometres only). As a vehicle is moving, it should remain connected to the closest server to minimise latency. We refer to this problem as “MEC handover”.

Some cloud services, such as parking or traffic services, may also be localised. Therefore, in the same way as for MEC, they may require handover.

To implement this handover mechanism, we will use a geo service. Such a geo service will provide vehicles with the information required to connect to the closest or most (geographically) relevant services, including their capabilities and the functionality they support.

As can be seen in Figure 15, the geo service should include a registry of all the available services and their capabilities and connection details. A web API will allow vehicles to retrieve the details of MEC servers relevant to their locations or planned routes.

Figure 15 – ICT4CART Geo Service

5.2.4 Parking and Charging Station Service Gateway

The parking and charging station service gateway should provide common integrated access to parking and charging services. In addition, it should provide analytics services to predict parking and charging station availability and recommend parking and charging location to vehicles.

Figure 16 – Parking and Charging Station Service Gateway

An example architecture for the parking and charging station service gateway is provided in Figure 16. As can be seen in this architectural diagram, parking and charging station availability data may be collected from a variety of service providers or sensors through a broker component. Data is then stored in a log or database using a common data format and structure. The data may be accessible through a parking and charging data access service. Prediction model builder analyses the historical data to learn prediction models, which are then stored in an appropriate repository or database. A prediction service predicts in real time the availability of parking and charging station over a given time horizon (to be defined). An assignment module recommends suitable parking sites or spots and charging stations to vehicles.

The parking and charging station service gateway may be common across all the pilot sites or may be localised. Either way, the interfaces to query parking and charging station availability should comply with a common specification (same protocols, APIs, and data models).

5.2.5 Risk Maps for Automation Level Adaptation

A risk map provider component may be implemented to provide common access to context data required by the AD vehicle to assess the risk pertaining to driving in a given automation level. Data required to build the risk maps may be provided by various data sources, such as traffic control centres, MEC services, RSUs, etc. For the automation level adaptation use case, risk maps may be provided through a common interface (risk map API as illustrated in Figure 17) across the pilot sites to ensure interoperability.

Figure 17 – Risk Maps for Automation Level Adaptation

5.2.6 Collective Perception Service

A collective perception service (CPS) provides environment perception models (EPMs) to vehicles. Such EPMs provide information describing the physical environment (vehicles, pedestrians, objects) at a given location.

EPMs may be built by fusing data from multiple sources as illustrated in the example architecture of

Figure 18. Data from multiple sources may be processed to build environment perception models. Data source may include road sensors (e.g., camera, LIDAR), road side units, and other road users. Such processing may be performed close to the sensor (e.g., sensor itself or RSU), or to the collective perception service itself (e.g., same MEC server as the CPS), or on both. A collective perception service is then responsible for delivering the EPMs to the vehicles through standardised interfaces and protocols.

Figure 18 – Collective Perception Service

5.2.7 Environmental Notification Service

Vehicles need to be aware of events and situations occurring in their surroundings. This is essential for the automated driving functions or for the adaptation thereof. As events and situations are not covered by environment perception models, they should be communicated using appropriate standard services. The ETSI Decentralised Environmental Notification Basic Service specification [DENM14] should be adopted for this purpose.

6 Environment Perception Models

An environment perception model (EPM) is the way in which a system represents the surrounding environment. The representation is based on the information extracted from sensor data or received from other sources (e.g., awareness messages or other EPMs).

6.1 Introduction to Environment Perception Models

Automated vehicles require deep knowledge of the environment in which they operate in order to perform their manoeuvres. EPMs aim to supply the vehicle with the required environment information, such as information related to static and dynamic objects, road markings and traffic road signs. One of the main tasks of the automated driving function is to sense the environment to detect obstacles or provide information needed to make driving decisions. EPMs represent the method used to collect the data from different heterogeneous sensors and transfer the sensed information to the vehicle in a meaningful way.

EPMs are built using information from various sources such as:

- Sensors, e.g., radar, LIDAR, cameras,
- Other information sources, such as the GNSS system and/or (high-definition) maps,
- Other connected road actors, i.e., other connected vehicles or roadside units that can share their dynamic information, their local sensors information, or their EPMs.

EPMs may be built either at the vehicle-side (in a decentralised way) or at the roadside (in a centralised way), as shown in Figure 19. Both approaches strongly influence the information flow. In the ICT4CART project, information is exchanged as ETSI standard messages where possible. Existing ETSI message standards relevant to the scope of EPM building exist for information pertaining to road topology (MAP messages), traffic light information (SPAT messages), traffic road signs (infrastructure to vehicle, IVI, messages [IVI16]), information about the ITS station (CAM) and other information from ITS stations, including information about non-ITS-equipped objects, detected by ITS station sensors (CPM) see Section 6.4. Additional custom messages (or extensions of standard messages) may be considered for the exchange of information not foreseen by current standards but required by the ICT4CART use cases.

Figure 19 – Two Example Scenarios for Building EPMs: Vehicle-Side and Roadside

In the vehicle-side scenario, the information received by each vehicle is used to build an EPM that may

differ from vehicle to vehicle since information received from external sources can be potentially different and each vehicle can process the information in different ways. In the roadside scenario, all the information flows are received by a single entity that is in charge of building the EPM and sharing it with all the road users. The roadside EPM is restricted to a well-defined area, such as a road intersection, toll station, slip road, etc.

In both scenarios, the connected and automated vehicle has to maintain a local EPM that is based on its own instruments and possibly integrating the EPMs received from the roadside. The vehicle might have to transform the roadside EPM considering its own coordinate system.

In addition to sharing EPMs with vehicles, roadside entities may implement other applications using information available in the EPMs they generate. For example, a roadside entity may warn vehicles about potentially dangerous situations, such as collisions, using standard DENM. This example can be based on the motion prediction activity introduced in Section 7.1.3.

Since ICT4CART aims to demonstrate how the roadside infrastructure may support connected and automated vehicles, the target architecture focuses on building EPMs at the roadside rather than the vehicle side.

To cope with the edge computing requirements of the roadside EPM building approach, a MEC infrastructure will be used. MEC servers will receive data and information from various road sensors and road users to build EPMs and share them with vehicles (cf. Figure 19-b) within low latency. This has the advantage of providing the required computing power for fusing data and information from multiple sensors and road users.

EPMs will be used in the following ICT4CART use cases:

- **Virtual Mirror:** The connected and automated vehicle will benefit from the information in the EPM to learn about other road actors that may not be directly perceivable by the vehicle, e.g., due to a physical obstruction in an urban environment.
- **Lane Merging:** The connected and automated vehicle will exploit the information about incoming vehicles present in the EPM to merge smoothly into the highway.
- **Wrong-Way Driving:** The “wrong way driving” information from the EPM will be exploited by the vehicle or by a monitoring application on a roadside unit to check whether another vehicle is driving in the wrong direction of a lane or road. This is part of the lane merging use case of the Italian test site.

6.2 Representation of EPMs

The main aspect concerning EPMs is their representation. Different methods may be used, but the most common ones are, as reported in [VU09]:

- **Object-Based:** An object-based representation encodes each dynamic traffic participant (e.g., vehicle, pedestrian, cyclist) as an object. An object may have specific attributes, such as a probability of existence (as sensor information and processing algorithms are uncertain), its classification (e.g., the aforementioned types of traffic participants), its spatial extent (width, height, length), dynamic features such as velocity and acceleration, a motion history in the form of a past trajectory or predictions of possible future trajectories, as well as uncertainty or confidence level information (e.g., probabilities or covariance matrices) for these attributes.
- **Feature-Based:** Feature map representation assumes that the environment consists of a set of isolated features representing the content of the environment. In general, features are represented with geometric primitives, e.g., points, lines, circles, polygons. Geometric

representation has the advantage of being easy to implement and requiring low memory usage. However, it is not convenient for depicting complex environments because they rely on a previous knowledge of the targets and could have problems with moving objects or in representing the space in between the features and natural structures.

- **Grid-Based:** Grid-map representation splits the environment into a grid of rectangular cells. The resolution of the environment representation directly depends on the cells size. A probabilistic measure of occupancy is estimated for each cell of the grid which indicates whether a cell is occupied by an obstacle or not. There also exist solutions of dynamic grids, which also estimate and encode velocities for each cell, which can be used to extract dynamic entities.
- **Direct-Based:** Direct-map representation uses raw data measurements to represent the physical environment without extracting predefined features. This method is introduced when range sensors like LIDAR are used; in this case the map can be constructed through the elaboration of point cloud data.
- **Topological-Based:** topological maps are usually generated on top of grid-based or feature-based maps by partitioning them into coherent regions.

The collective perception service (see Section 6.4) that is responsible for delivering perception models may support of one or more of the above representations.

6.3 Content of an EPM

The information present in an EPM can strongly differ based on the available sensors and on the type of processing performed on the sensor data to extract features or objects. In the ICT4CART project, since the focus is on the roadside infrastructure support to connected and automated vehicles, the EPM will mainly contain information concerning dynamic (moving) objects. Information about stationary objects (such as traffic road signs) and road topology is expected to be provided either by messages according to ETSI TC ITS standards (i.e., IVI, MAP) or by in-vehicle information sources (i.e., high-definition augmented maps). The information interference and fusion to build the EPM also uses information on the characteristics of the employed sensors and the area that they cover.

An EPM typically provides information about the current state of the environment. In the ICT4CART project, we strive to extend the classical concept of EPM to consider also the future state (predicted motion) of the environment. This information, even if subject to an intrinsic uncertainty, may help connected and automated vehicle to anticipate situation and better plan their maneuvers, e.g., in the virtual mirror or lane merging uses cases.

6.4 Relevant standards

In ICT4CART, we aim to adopt relevant standards for the implementation of EPMs. This includes both the message contents and the exchange interfaces. This said, some components of the EPM implementation may be proprietary.

The ETSI standardisation organisation, within the Technical Committee on ITS, has already developed CAM standards to allow ITS stations to regularly broadcast information about their statuses. But the CAM standard is only usable by road users or sensors equipped with ITS stations as described in [CAM14] and in [ITS-S10].

In order to allow information about non-equipped road users and objects (detected by sensors of an ITS Station) to be transmitted to other ITS stations, ETSI TC ITS has started the development of the Collective Perception Service in 2017 with two work items:

- ETSI TR 103 562, Technical report for the “Analysis of the Collective Perception Service (CPS)”, which is expected to be published by the end of 2019,
- ETSI TS 103 324, Technical Specification of the Collective Perception Service, which is expected to be published by mid-2020.

It is understood that these two work items are not publicly available before their publication as ETSI Technical Report or ETSI Technical Specification.

The ETSI CPS standard aims to enable ITS stations to be aware of road users (e.g., vehicles, objects, pedestrians) detected by sensors connected to another ITS station. This is achieved through the exchange of collective perception messages (CPMs). The CPS standard provides the data format and ASN.1 encoding of the CPM, as well as the implementation of the CPS, with the relevant interfaces, in the ITS architecture.

However, the CPS standard does not address how EPMs are built or represented, in particular when EPMs are going to use different architectures than the ITS architecture referenced in [CAM14] and in [ITS-S10].

The ETSI Local Dynamic Map standard EN 302 895 [LDM14] defines the functions and interfaces supported by a Local Dynamic Map (LDM) entity, which aims to maintain on an ITS Station (i.e., vehicle or roadside unit) the information on objects influencing or influenced by road traffic. The LDM can receive such information from several different sources. Information providers can be either “*vehicles, infrastructure units, traffic centres, personal ITS stations, and on-board sensors and other applications*”, as per [LDM14].

An EPM implementation may use the information provided by the ETSI standardised TC ITS messages (CAM, DENM, CPM) or the dataset stored in an ETSI standardised TC ITS LDM.

To the best of our knowledge, there are not any other relevant standards to describe how to implement EPMs. The communication of the EPM information will be based on CPM as specified in the future ETSI CPS standard TS 103 324.

7 Data Analytics

The ICT4CART IT environment will provide data analytics to support the use cases introduced in Section 3. The data analytics required by the use cases are specified in the subsequent sections.

7.1 Data Analytics Types

In this section we define the data analytics to be developed in ICT4CART.

7.1.1 Prediction of Parking Availability

In the smart parking use case, the prediction of parking availability will help optimise the vehicle parking locations and plans. The prediction of parking availability should rely on historical parking availability data from service providers.

Parking availability historical data may be obtained directly from the service provider (if available) or compiled over time using real-time data.

Additional context information (e.g., weather, traffic, etc.) may be used to improve the prediction. This is subject to data availability.

Several methods may be used to predict parking availability, such as deep learning, or time series analysis methods.

The parking prediction analytics may support one or multiple test sites.

7.1.2 Prediction of Charging Station Availability

In the smart parking use case, the prediction of charging station availability will help optimise the vehicle parking locations and charging plans. The prediction of charging station availability should rely on historical charging station data from service providers. These may be obtained directly from the service provider (if available) or compiled over time using real-time data.

Several methods may be used to predict charging station availability, such as deep learning, or time series analysis methods.

7.1.3 Motion Prediction for Environment Perception Models

An environment perception model (EPM) consists of information about the objects at a given location (e.g., intersection, slip road, toll station, etc.). Such information is essential for the AD vehicle to operate safely (e.g., virtual mirror and intersection crossing use case). The vehicle needs to understand not only the positions of the objects around it, but also their intentions (e.g., their future movements). Therefore, environment perception models should include the predictions of the behaviours of the objects in question.

In ICT4CART, we will strive to implement analytics methods to predict the behaviour of the objects included in EPMs. Such predictions should take into account the current observations about the objects (position, speed, heading, etc.), and, possibly, the characteristics of the physical environment itself (manoeuvre restrictions, physical obstacles, etc.).

While it can be argued that motion prediction should be part of the EPM activity, common or generic analytics methods that may underpin motion prediction may be considered as part of the analytics activity if they can be provided as generic core services.

7.1.4 Risk Maps for the Adaptation of Automation Level

The adaptation of the vehicle automation level requires an understanding of the environment in which the vehicle is operating, and the various situations and events that may occur, e.g., traffic jams ahead, incidents, cyber-security attack in a certain area, etc. We refer to such information as “risk maps”. Although the risk assessment itself is left to the vehicle, such maps will provide the data required by the vehicles to assess the risk of driving in any given automation level.

The generation of risk maps may be based on existing data from traffic control centres (TCCs) but may also include additional knowledge generated using data analytics. Whether data analytics will be used to generate risk maps or not will be decided at later stages of the project.

7.2 Data Analytics per Use Case and Test Site

A summary of the data analytics and their relevance to the use cases and test sites is shown in Table 3 below.

Table 3 –Data Analytics and Use Cases

Analytics	UC 1			UC 2			UC 3			UC 4
	Germany	Austria	Italy	Germany	Austria	Italy	Germany	Austria	Italy	
Prediction of Parking Availability	X									
Prediction of Charging Station Availability	X									
Motion Prediction for Environment Perception Models				X	X	X	X	X	X	
Risk Maps for the Adaptation of Automation Level					X			X		

7.3 Architecture

Data analytics may not be centralised in ICT4CART as there may not be a single data analytics platform or infrastructure suitable for all the use cases in all the test sites. In addition, it is not practical or scalable, sometimes even possible, to stream all the analytics input data to a central platform. Instead, various data analytics components and platforms may be implemented in different infrastructures (clouds, MEC servers, etc.) to cope with the requirements of the various use cases and test sites. Nevertheless, we recommend that the data analytics components may implement common software architecture patterns, such as Lambda or Kappa architectures.

Figure 20 shows an example Kappa architecture that may be followed to implement the ICT4CART data analytics components. As can be seen in this architectural diagram, data from various sources (e.g., road sensors, vehicles, TCCs) may be fed into the analytics architecture through a message broker. Data are then stored in an append-only immutable log store. Note that the broker is optional, any other data ingestion mechanism may be considered. But since very popular brokering

technologies, such as Apache Kafka⁵, include both a broker and a distributed log, the combination of a broker with a log seems natural.

A streaming platform such as Apache Spark Streaming⁶ allows the analytics components to process the logged data both online and offline. Results of the analytics may be stored in a database and exchanged with external services through a serving layer.

Figure 20 – Example Data Analytics Kappa Architecture

The above architecture has several advantages, including the following.

- The architecture allows both online and offline analytics to be performed using a generic architecture.
- You only need to re-process the data when you change the processing method or code.
- Since the data is logged and is immutable, if you need to re-process the data, you just need to start new stream instance from the beginning of the log.
- You can check if the new processing version is working properly and roll back to the older version if not.

⁵ Apache Kafka Website: <https://kafka.apache.org>

⁶ Apache Spark Streaming Website: <https://spark.apache.org/streaming>

8 Semantic Interoperability

In ICT4CART we seek to demonstrate interoperability not only at the network (telecommunication) level, but also at the IT service level. Therefore, similar IT environment services should be accessible in the same way regardless of their location. For instance, a vehicle should be able to communicate with a parking provider gateway in the same way whether this is deployed in Germany or Italy, etc. In the same way, similar services deployed on MEC should be accessible in the same way.

A large part of interoperability is taken care of by standards (e.g., ETSI specifications). However, standards may have limitations, as they may leave some degree of freedom to the vocabularies used for some data fields. Common examples of such fields are: parking spot categories or types, detected object types, etc. When not designed properly, such fields may hinder interoperability, as we may end up with field values that vary from one pilot site to another and from one organisation to another, thus leading to semantic interoperability issues.

In ICT4CART, we strive to solve the semantic interoperability issue by providing a semantic framework to:

1. Standardise the vocabularies used by the various IT services of the architecture,
2. Define the semantic relationships between the terms of the vocabularies to allow for advanced reasoning functionality or to link heterogeneous vocabularies,
3. To overcome the language issues (e.g., German vs. Italian vs. English).

The nature of the semantic framework and its architecture have already been discussed in Section 5.2.2. This Section focuses on the identifying the scope for semantic interoperability and the potentially relevant vocabularies or ontologies to adopt or create. A preliminary scoping of the use of vocabularies or ontologies is provided in Table 4 below.

Table 4 – Initial Scoping of Semantic Interoperability Requirements

Scope	Use Case or Service	Reason
Parking availability data	Smart Parking	Standardised parking categories and types
Charging station availability data	Smart Parking	Standardised charging station types
Environment perception models	Intersection crossing and automation level adaptation	Standardised object types, standardised sensor types, brands and models
Risk maps	Adaptation of automation level	Standardised risk factor types
Service metadata	Geo service	Standardised service types

9 Precise Localisation

9.1 Overview

The precise localisation service is based on the Real-Time Kinematic (RTK) technique, which enhances the precision of the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) by using carrier phase measurements and correction data of RTK reference stations, thus achieving an accuracy up to 1-2cm + 1ppm (CEP) in case of optimal reception conditions at the client side.

The proposals for the future ICT4CART architecture, to provide such a service to clients (so-called rovers), intend to use a unique GNSS precise localisation service in a MEC server. A MEC Server may use correction data provided either by an external service provider (e.g. SAPOS) or by dedicated RTK reference stations collocated with the 4G/5G mobile radio network.

There are different ways for transmitting the correction data to the clients, such as point to point or broadcast/multicast transport mechanisms. The standard transport mechanism is a point to point connection using a Networked Transport of RTCM via Internet Protocol (NTRIP) service based on the Radio Technical Commission for Maritime Services (RTCM) standard. Other transport mechanisms that allow to use point to point or broadcast/multicast connections are provided by the C-ITS or the 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) standard. Currently, these standards are not yet mature, therefore, only point to point connection is considered.

9.2 German Test Site Approach

In the German test site, an RTK reference station will be collocated with each 4G/5G radio base station. The distance between different 4G/5G radio base stations are typically no more than 10 km. The RTK technique requires that the distance between the reference station and the client shall be no more than 10 km in order to achieve the guaranteed accuracy.

Figure 21 – German Test Site Approach for Precise Localisation

Therefore, the MEC server simply can select the nearest RTK reference station, in order to provide the appropriate correction data to the client. The MEC server will provide the correction data to the clients by a NTRIP server compliant with the RTCM standard (see Figure 21). The required point to point

connection is based on a 4G/5G radio link.

As an option, the MEC server can combine correction data from different RTK reference stations in order to achieve the guaranteed accuracy even in difficult environments, such as urban areas, similar to the approach used in Network RTK.

9.3 Austrian Test Site Approach

In the Austrian test site, the precise localisation service is completely based on a Network RTK approach, because the distance between the different RTK reference stations is significantly larger than 10 km in the case of an external service provider.

The MEC server will use correction data from an external service provider (e.g., SAPOS) and behaves more or less as a proxy server between the client and the external service provider. The advantage of this approach is that the MEC server can provide a unique localisation service to the clients, independent from the individual external service provider in the different countries. Furthermore, the MEC server can use one set of correction data for a cluster of clients, e.g., all clients located in one 4G/5G radio cell (see Figure 22).

Figure 22 – Austrian Test Site Approach for Precise Localisation

10 Conclusion

The first version of the IT environment specification and architecture (task T3.3 of ICT4CART) is presented. The scope of the ICT4CART IT environment is described and an initial specification of the functions and components is presented. A high-level architecture as well as more detailed architectures focused on the various components are presented. In particular, the ICT4CART IT environment architecture is introduced to cover data exchange and management aspects, data analytics, semantic interoperability, environment perception models (EPM), and high-precision positioning.

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